

Supplementary material 5: Rarefaction curves for each sample indicating that 35,243 reads (black dotted vertical line) was selected to obtain an accurate assessment of ASV richness. One sample was suppressed from the analysis as its number of reads was too below (19,764 reads, red dotted vertical line). See Supplementary material 3 for correspondence between the codes displayed in the figure and the sample information (station, period, replicate number) in the present study.

